

Bivalent copper compounds with tridentate ligands supported by two labile donors : Syntheses, structure, magnetic and spectroscopic properties

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Abstract : Two new mononuclear copper(II) complexes with tridentate ligands (L1 and L2 = tridentate ligand derived from condensation of 2-benzoylpyridine and *N,N*-dimethylethylenediamine and *N,N*-diethylethylenediamine respectively) supported by two labile donors (thiocyanato and perchlorato anions) [Cu(L1)(NCS)(ClO₄)] (1) and [Cu(L2)(NCS)(ClO₄)] (2) have been synthesized, studied their spectroscopic properties and characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. These two compounds exhibit magnetic moment corresponding very close to spin only value of one unpaired electron thereby ruling out the possibility of any electronic communication between paramagnetic copper(II) partners in the structural unit. The X-ray data actually confirm this from the mononuclear nature of these two complexes. Compound 1 crystallizes in orthorhombic space group Pna2(1) with unit cell dimension $a = 9.2534(1) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 26.9181(3) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 8.1508(1) \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $Z = 4$ and compound 2 consist of orthorhombic space group Pbca with unit cell dimension $a = 15.7006(2) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 13.3052(2) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 21.6021(3) \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $Z = 8$. In the both compounds copper is surrounded by a distorted square pyramidal (CuN₄O) environment consisting of three nitrogen atoms from the tridentate ligand, one nitrogen atom from terminal labile thiocyanate moiety and one oxygen atom from the second labile perchlorate anion attached to copper atom.

Keywords : Copper(II) complexes, pentacoordination, single crystal structure, square pyramidal, thiocyanate, perchlorate coordination.

Introduction

In the last couple of decades there has been phenomenal advancement in the area of coordination chemistry of transition metals with Schiff base ligands due to their significant role as redox active site in numerous reactions in biosphere¹, the diversity of their magnetic properties² and building blocks of supramolecular architecture through variety of non-covalent intermolecular interactions³, their fascinating structures⁴ and rich physical properties^{5,6}. Because of their preparative accessibility and structural variability a great number of Schiff base complexes of copper have been the subject of extensive studies and are of much interest in catalysis⁷ and in small molecule binding^{8,9}. The stereochemical flexibility of bivalent copper compounds allow to adopt a wide range of coordination geometries as compare to other transition metals¹. Copper sites are ubiquitous in nature and perform a wide variety of functions, such as amine oxidase, galactase oxidase, and nitrite reductase¹⁰. Mononuclear copper com-

plexes have shown potential drugs for genetic disorders such as thalassemia^{11,12}. In the last decades a large number of copper(II) complexes have been prepared and structurally studied in attempt to mimic the potent inhibitor properties of DNA synthesis^{13,14}. Recently copper complexes have been extensively utilized in metal-mediated DNA cleavage¹⁵⁻¹⁹ and anti-HIV activities and also used in the treatment of cancer²⁰. On the basis and importance's of the findings, we started to explore the chemistry copper(II) complexes using tridentate Schiff base ligands and labile donors like thiocyanato and perchlorato anions. As DNA cleavage may take place via oxidative or hydrolytic pathways and use of labile donors have already been recognized.

We report herein the synthesis, characterisation, spectroscopic and magnetic properties of two bivalent copper complexes [Cu(L1)(NCS)(ClO₄)] (1) and [Cu(L2)(NCS)(ClO₄)] (2) (L1 and L2 = tridentate ligand derived from condensation of 2-benzoylpyridine and *N,N*-

dimethylethylenediamine and *N,N*-diethylethylenediamine, respectively). The single crystal X-ray structure of these two compounds confirms the presence of two labile donors thiocyanato and perchlorato anions coordinated to copper centres along with tridentate ligand moiety.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The reaction of ligand L1 or L2 with $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NH_4NCS using a ratio of L1 or L2 : Cu^{II} : $\text{NCS}^- = 1 : 1 : 1$ in methanol medium affords blue crystalline compounds suitable for X-ray crystallography having composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{L1})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (1) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L2})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (2). Microanalytical results (please see Experimental section, *vide infra*) are in line with proposed formulation. In acetonitrile both the compounds behave as non-electrolyte²¹, as indicated by their very low Λ_M values ($5\text{--}7 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$).

Magnetic susceptibility study :

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the two compounds in the polycrystalline form show that the complexes are paramagnetic at room temperature. The observed magnetic moments of these complexes are 1.78 BM (for compound 1) and 1.82 BM (for compound 2) at 300 K corresponds to $t_{2g}^6 e_g^3$, $S = \frac{1}{2}$ electronic configura-

tion with one unpaired electron as expected for copper(II) monomeric paramagnetic species²².

Infrared spectral behaviour :

The stretching vibrations of ClO_4^- for these complexes are found at around 1100, 650 and 623 cm^{-1} . The band at 650 cm^{-1} is due to perchlorate anion coordination^{23,24}. The IR spectrum of 1, 2 exhibits a bands respectively at 2082 and 2094 cm^{-1} corresponding to the asymmetric stretching vibrations of the ligand NCS^- , which are similar to those previously reported^{25,26}. The stretching vibrations for the C=N bond of both the Schiff bases L1 and L2 are located respectively at 1647 and 1649 cm^{-1} which is shifted to lower energies (around 1610 cm^{-1}) in the spectra of the two complexes indicating the coordination via the azomethine nitrogen which have been further substantiated by single crystal X-ray data (*vide infra*)^{25,27}.

Description of the crystal structures of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L1})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (1) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L2})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (2) :

The ORTEP drawing of the complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{L1})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (1) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L2})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (2) are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively and the selected bond distances and angles are listed in Table 1. Copper is in a distorted square pyramidal (CuN_4O) coordination environment consisting of one N atom (N4) from N-bonded thiocyanate anion and three N atoms (N1, N2 and N3) from Schiff

Fig. 1. ORTEP plot with atom numbering scheme for $[\text{Cu}(\text{L1})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (1). For clarity the hydrogen atoms are not shown.

Fig. 2. ORTEP plot with atom numbering scheme for $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}2)(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (2). For clarity the hydrogen atoms are not shown

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles ($^\circ$) for the compounds $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}1)(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (1) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}2)(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (2)

Bond distances	$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}1)(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (1)	$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}2)(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (2)
Cu-N(1)	2.019(3)	2.0242(17)
Cu-N(2)	1.935(3)	1.9340(17)
Cu-N(3)	2.047(3)	2.0635(17)
Cu-N(4)	1.913(3)	1.912(2)
Cu-O (perchlorate)	2.531(6)	2.5388(19)
N(4)-C(6)	1.151(5)	1.149(3)
C(6)-S(1)	1.607(4)	1.614(2)
Bond angles	$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}1)(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (1)	$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}2)(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (2)
N(1)-Cu-N(2)	80.18(13)	80.46(7)
N(1)-Cu-N(3)	164.59(13)	161.68(7)
N(1)-Cu-N(4)	98.30(14)	98.59(8)
N(2)-Cu-N(3)	84.56(13)	84.40(7)
N(2)-Cu-N(4)	174.22(14)	177.98(8)
N(3)-Cu-N(4)	97.10(15)	96.84(8)
N(1)-Cu-O (perchlorate)	87.67(16)	83.48(7)
N(2)-Cu-O (perchlorate)	89.58(16)	88.09(7)
N(3)-Cu-O (perchlorate)	90.14(17)	106.38(7)
N(4)-Cu-O (perchlorate)	95.94(18)	90.03(7)

base ligand and the rest oxygen atom from coordinated perchlorate anion for both compounds. The four nitrogen

atoms occupy the basal position while oxygen occupy the axial position. The Cu-N distances are ranging from 1.913(3) to 2.047(3) Å for compound 1 and 1.912(2) to 2.0635(17) Å for compound 2. The distance between the copper and axial oxygen atom of perchlorate ion is 2.531(6) and 2.5388(19) Å for compound 1 and 2 respectively^{28,29}. The Cu-N (thiocyanate) distances are considerably shorter than Cu-N ligand distances as expected due to stronger binding capability of NCS^- anion compared to that of neutral polydentate ligands^{30,31}. The Cu-NCS distances are in good agreement with those found in the literature^{32,33}. The thiocyanate group are coordinated in a slight bent fashion $[\text{Cu}(1)-\text{N}(4)-\text{C}(6)]$: $170.7(4)^\circ$ for complex 1 and $164.27(19)^\circ$ for complex 2. Analysis of angular structural parameter, τ , as a general descriptor of five coordinate centric molecule reveals that both the compounds undergoes slight distortion from regular square pyramidal geometry. The magnitude of angular structural parameter (τ) is 0.16 and 0.27 for compound 1 and 2 respectively³⁴.

EPR behaviour :

The EPR spectra of these two copper(II) complexes were recorded at polycrystalline solid (at 77 K and at 298 K) and 1 : 1 CH_3CN -toluene glass and are isotropic in nature with a g value of 2.0. Considering the structural results (*vide supra*) these observations are rather surprising. The plausible explanation may be due to coordination of a solvent molecule and making the coordination sphere as relaxed octahedral.

Experimental

N,N-Dimethylethylenediamine, *N,N*-diethylethylenediamine, 2-benzoylpyridine, ammonium thiocyanate were obtained from Lancaster and Aldrich Chemical Company and were used as received. All other solvents and chemicals were of analytical grade.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analysis for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400II elemental analyzer. Copper content was determined titrimetrically. IR spectra (as KBr pellets, 4000–400 cm^{-1}) were taken at 298 K using a Shimadzu model 8400 S spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured at 300 K using a magnetometer (Sherwood Scientific Model MK1). Pascal's constants were utilized to estimate diamagnetic correction, which was subtracted from the experimental susceptibility data to give the corrected molar magnetic susceptibility (χ_M). X-band EPR spectra were recorded at room temperature (298 K) and also at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K) on a Varian E-109C spectrometer fitted with a quartz Dewar flask for low-temperature measurements. DPPH ($g = 2.0037$) was used to calibrate the EPR spectra.

Synthesis of ligands :

Both the ligands L1 and L2 (Scheme 1) were prepared by condensation of amine and aldehyde. For L1, *N,N*-dimethylethylenediamine (0.88 g, 10 mmol) and 2-benzoylpyridine (1.83 g, 10 mmol) were refluxed in 25 ml dehydrated alcohol for 6 h. The tridentate ligand was isolated as brown semisolid mass after evaporating the solvent as well as recrystallised from dehydrated alcohol and water and drying in a vacuum over P_4O_{10} . Yield : 1.82 g (~ 75%) (Found : C, 75.8; H, 7.4; N, 16.5. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3$: C, 75.9; H, 7.5; N, 16.6%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 1647. For L2, a similar procedure was adopted except that *N,N*-dimethylethylenediamine was replaced by an equimolar quantity of *N,N*-diethylethylenediamine (1.16 g, 10 mmol). Brown semisolid mass was isolated as be-

fore. Yield : 1.95 g (~ 70%) (Found : C, 76.8; H, 8.1; N, 14.8. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_3$: C, 76.8; H, 8.2; N, 14.9%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 1649.

Synthesis of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L1})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (1) :

For the preparation of compound 1, a methanolic solution (10 ml) of the L1 (0.126 g, 0.5 mmol) was added slowly to a methanolic solution (10 ml) of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.186 g, 0.5 mmol). To the resulting blue solution methanolic solution (5 ml) of ammonium thiocyanate (0.038 g, 0.5 mmol) solution was added slowly. Then the solution was filtered and filtrate was kept for slow evaporation. After 3–4 days deep blue crystals of 1 were obtained which were suitable for X-ray crystallography. Yield : 0.148 g (~ 60%) (Found : C, 43.0; H, 3.8; N, 11.7; Cu, 13.2. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4\text{ClO}_4\text{SCu}$: C, 43.0; H, 4.0; N, 11.8; Cu, 13.4%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 2082, 1610, 1595, 1103, 650, 623.

Synthesis of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L2})(\text{NCS})(\text{ClO}_4)]$ (2) :

The compound 2 was synthesized following the same procedure as described for 1, except that L1 was replaced by equimolar quantity of L2. After 3–4 days deep blue crystals of 2 were obtained which were suitable for X-ray crystallography. Yield : 0.174 g (~ 70%) (Found : C, 45.4; H, 4.4; N, 11.1; Cu, 12.2. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_4\text{ClO}_4\text{SCu}$: C, 45.4; H, 4.6; N, 11.2; Cu, 12.6%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 2094, 1610, 1596, 1101, 650, 623.

Caution : Perchlorate salts are potentially explosive especially in presence of organic ligands. Therefore, these compounds must be handled with care and prepared only in small amounts.

Crystal structure determinations and refinement :

The X-ray diffraction data were collected at 296 K with $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) using a Bruker Nonius SMART CCD diffractometer equipped with a graphite monochromator. Smart software was used for data collection and also for indexing the reflections and determining the unit cell parameters; the collected data were integrated using saint software. The structures were solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least-squares calculations using SHELXTL³⁵ software. All the non-H atoms were refined in the anisotropic approximation. The crystallographic parameters of the compounds studied are given in Table 2.

Scheme 1

Table 2. Crystal data and data collection summary for compounds 1 and 2

Empirical formula	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄ ClSCu	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄ ClSCu
Formula weight	474.43	502.48
Crystal system	Orthorhombic	Orthorhombic
Space group	Pna2 (1)	Pbca
<i>a</i> (Å)	9.2534(1)	15.7006(2)
<i>b</i> (Å)	26.9181(3)	13.3052(2)
<i>c</i> (Å)	8.1508(1)	21.6021(3)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	2030.23(4)	4512.67(11)
<i>Z</i>	4	8
ρ_{calcd} (g/cm ³)	1.552	1.479
<i>F</i> (000)	972	2072
Crystal size (mm)	0.15 × 0.28 × 0.40	0.15 × 0.30 × 0.45
μ (Mo K α) (mm)	1.341	1.211
λ (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Temperature (K)	296	296
$2\theta_{\text{max}}$ (°)	28.3	28.3
Reflections collected	22617	51272
Independent reflections	4513 [<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.023]	5624 [<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.030]
Reflections observed [<i>I</i> > 2.0 σ (<i>I</i>)]	3755	4286
Goodness-of-fit	1.06	1.04
<i>R</i> ; <i>wR</i>	0.0401; 0.1146	0.0355; 0.0970
Largest difference peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	0.57 and -0.3	0.57 and -0.38

Conclusions :

The present study describes the two new mononuclear copper(II) complexes with tridentate ligands (L1 and L2 = tridentate ligand derived from condensation of 2-benzoylpyridine, *N,N*-dimethylethylenediamine and *N,N*-diethylethylenediamine respectively) supported by two labile donors (thiocyanato and perchlorato anions) [Cu(L1)(NCS)(ClO₄)] (1) and [Cu(L2)(NCS)(ClO₄)] (2) have been synthesized, studied their spectroscopic and magnetic properties and characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. Both the complexes 1 and 2 have distorted square pyramidal arrangements around the copper centre in which basal positions are occupied by the four nitrogen atoms (three from tridentate Schiff bases and one from labile thiocyanato anion) and axial position is coordinated through oxygen atom of the another labile perchlorato anion. The degree of distortion is 16% for 1 while for 2 it is 27% from the regular square pyramidal geometry. The magnetic moments in polycrystalline form are 1.78 BM (for compound 1) and 1.82 BM (for com-

pound 2) at 300 K corresponds to $t_{2g}^6e_g^3$, $S = \frac{1}{2}$ electronic configuration with one unpaired electron as expected for one electron paramagnetic species. The EPR behaviour was surprising and possible explanation have been provided. To the best of our knowledge, these two copper(II) compounds are the first report of pentacoordinated bivalent copper coordinated by two potentially labile donors perchlorato and thiocyanato anions. The synthesis of compounds using other ligand backbone with these two labile donors to copper and other transition metal ions are in progress.

Supplementary material available :

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC No. 719759 and 719760 for the compounds 1 and 2 respectively. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www:http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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References

1. F. A. Cotton, G. Wilkinson, C. A. Murillo and M. Bochmann, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 6th ed., John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1999.
2. O. Kahn, "Molecular Magnetism", VCH, New York, 1993.
3. J.-M. Lehn, "Supramolecular Chemistry, Concepts and Perspectives", VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 1995.
4. (a) A. Müller, *Science*, 2003, **300**, 74; (b) A. L. Dearden, S. Parsons and R. E. P. Winpenny, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2001, **40**, 151; (c) D. Fenske, C. Persau, S. Dehnen and C. E. Anson, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2004, **43**, 305.
5. (a) P. C. Ford, E. Cariati and J. Bourassa, *J. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **99**, 3625. (b) V. W.-W. Yam and K. K.-W. Lo, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1999, **28**, 323.
6. (a) J. T. Brockman, J. C. Huffman and G. Christou, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2002, **41**, 2506; (b) E. K. Brechin, C. Boskovic, W. Wernsdorfer, J. Yoo, A. Yamaguchi, E. C. Sanudo, T. R. Concolino, A. L. Rheingold, H. Ishimoto, D.

- N. Hendrickson and G. Christou, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 9710; (c) A. Müller and C. Serain, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2000, **33**, 2.
7. E. N. Jacobsen, W. Zhang, A. R. Muci, J. R. Ecker and L. Deng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 7063.
 8. E. C. Neiderhoffer, J. E. Timmons and A. E. Martell, *Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **84**, 137.
 9. D. Chen and A. E. Martell, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 1026.
 10. (a) R. H. Holm, P. Kennepohl and E. I. Solomon, *Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **96**, 2239; (b) E. I. Solomon, R. Sarangi, J. S. Woertink, A. J. Augustine, J. Yoon and S. Ghosh, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2007, **40**, 581.
 11. J. D. Ranford, J. J. Vittal and M. Wang Yu, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 1226.
 12. M. L. Vitollo, J. J. Webb and P. Saltman, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1984, **20**, 255.
 13. D. K. Johnson, T. B. Murphy, N. J. Bose, W. H. Goodwin and L. Pickart, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, **67**, 59.
 14. L. Pickart, W. H. Goodwin, W. Burgua, T. B. Murphy and D. K. Johnson, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1983, **32**, 3868.
 15. C. L. Liu, J. Y. Zhou, Q. X. Li, L. J. Wang, Z. R. Liao and H. B. Xu, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1999, **75**, 233.
 16. J. Liu, H. Zhang, C. Chen, H. Deng, T. Lu and L. Ji, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2003, 114.
 17. A. K. Patra, S. Dhar, M. Nethaji and A. R. Chakravarty, *Chem. Commun.*, 2003, 1562.
 18. H. Prakash, A. Shodal, H. Yasui, H. Sakurai and S. Hirota, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **47**, 5045.
 19. Z.-L. Lu, C. T. Liu, A. A. Neverov and R. S. Brown, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 11642.
 20. (a) M. Shionoyan and E. Kimura, *Chemistry*, 1992, **47**, 878; (b) J. R. J. Sorensen, *Chem. Br.*, 1984, **16**, 1110; (c) R. K. Gouch, T. W. Kensler, L. W. Oberly and L. W. Sorensen in : "Biochemical and Inorganic Copper Chemistry", eds. K. D. Karlin and J. Zubieta, Vol. 1, Adinine, New York, 1980, p. 139.
 21. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
 22. O. Kahn, "Molecular Magnetism", VCH, New York, 1993.
 23. D. L. Lewis, E. D. Estes and D. J. Hodgson, *J. Cryst. Mol. Struct.*, 1975, **5**, 67.
 24. M. Sekizaki, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1981, **54**, 146.
 25. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1997.
 26. M. Habib, T. K. Karmakar, G. Aromi, J. R. Arino, H. K. Fun, S. Chantrapromma and S. K. Chandra, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **47**, 4109.
 27. S. Deoghoria, S. Sain, M. Soler, W. T. Wong, G. Christou, S. K. Bera and S. K. Chandra, *Polyhedron*, 2003, **22**, 257.
 28. S. M. M. Sony, M. Kuppayee, M. N. Ponnuswami, J. Manonmani, M. Kundasamy, K. Sivakumar and H. K. Fun, *Cryst. Res. Technol.*, 2006, **41**, 517.
 29. P. S. Mukherjee, T. K. Maji, G. Mostafa, W. Hibbs and N. R. Chaudhuri, *New J. Chem.*, 2001, **25**, 760.
 30. S. Deoghoria, G. Mostafa, T. H. Lu and S. K. Chandra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 329.
 31. T. K. Karmakar, B. K. Ghosh and S. K. Chandra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, **45**, 1121.
 32. J. A. R. Navarro, M. A. Romero, J. M. Salas, M. Quiros and E. R. T. Tiekink, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1997, **36**, 4988.
 33. M. Kabesova, R. Boca, M. Melnik, D. Valigura and M. Dunaj-Jurco, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **140**, 115.
 34. A. W. Addison, T. N. Rao, J. Reedjik, J. V. Rijn and G. C. Verschoor, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1349.
 35. Sheldrick, G. M. SHELXTL, Bruker AXS : Madison, WI, 2005.